

62. Agroforestry and EU Corporate Sustainability Reporting

EURAF Policy Briefing 62 v1 23.1.25. Gerry Lawson (EURAF) 10.5281/zenodo.14724698

EURAF is an NGO, based in Montpellier and Brussels (Transparency Register ID of [913270437706-82](#)). It aims “to promote the adoption of agroforestry practices across Europe by supporting efforts to develop awareness, education, research, policy making and investments which foster the use of trees on farms”. It has a network of 31 affiliated entities in 23 countries.

Summary

Policy Briefing #62 (v2) points out the [significant simplification](#) introduced by the Commission on 26.2.25.

This simplification should be read in conjunction with the (v1) summary below of corporate sustainability reporting requirements introduced or proposed by the EU Commission, including the Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD), the Corporate Sustainability Due Diligence Directive (CSDDD), the Sustainable Finance Disclosures Regulation (SFDR), the Framework to Facilitate Sustainable Investment (SFI, aka “Taxonomy Regulation”) and the Green Claims Directive (GCD). Sustainability reporting in all these legislations is linked to methods developed by the European Financial Reporting Advisory Group, providing detailed guidance for reporting on environmental issues, including **climate change, pollution, water and marine resources, biodiversity and ecosystems, resource use and circular economy**; social issues, including own workforce, workers in the value chain, affected communities, consumers and end-users and governance issues related to business conduct. **The advantages of corporate support for agroforestry activities to address the environmental issues above is stressed and the publication “Agricultural trees for resilient landscapes: a vision for European agroforestry” (EURAF, December 2024) is introduced.**

What is Corporate Sustainability Reporting in the EU?

The EU Sustainability Reporting Standards (ESRS) are a set of standards that provide a framework for companies to report on environmental, social, and governance (ESG) topics. These standards were developed by the European Financial Reporting Advisory Group ([EFRAG](#)) and adopted by the European Commission in July 2023. They cover a wide range of sustainability topics, including: environmental (climate change, pollution, water and marine resources, biodiversity and ecosystems, resource use and circular economy); social (own workforce, workers in the value chain, affected communities, consumers and end-users); governance (business conduct). Standards relevant to this briefing are: ESRS E1 climate change ([EFRAG 2022a](#)), ESRS E2 pollution ([EFRAG 2022b](#)), ESRS E3 water and marine resources ([EFRAG 2022c](#)), ESRS E4 biodiversity and ecosystems ([EFRAG 2022d](#)), ESRS E5 resource use and circular economy ([EFRAG 2022e](#)).

These standards are a key part of the EU Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD), and the Corporate Sustainability Due Diligence Directive (CSDDD). Both Directives are complementary: the CSRD sets out the reporting requirements, while the CSDDD focuses on due diligence obligations related to environmental and social impacts in the value chain. Companies need to gather and report under both directives.

- The **Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD 2022/2464)** entered into force on 5 January 2023 and the first companies were required to apply the new rules for the financial year 2024, with reports published in 2025. They must report on their sustainability performance, including impacts, risks, and opportunities, focusing on transparency. The CSRD applies to a broad set of around 50,000 companies, including listed SMEs, and covers their entire "value chain" ([link](#)). Companies registered outside the EU have to report if they generate over EUR 150 million on the EU market. Companies must make detailed disclosures on their environmental policies, targets, risks, and performance, including: greenhouse gas emissions, water and energy consumption, waste management, pollution, biodiversity, use of resources. Companies are required to report on both the impact of their activities on sustainability issues and the impact of sustainability issues on their business ("double materiality"). Reports already published include companies like [Unilever](#), [Patagonia](#), [IKEA](#), [Microsoft](#), and [Nestle](#). A number of agricultural consultancies, like [AGRIVI](#), are providing reporting platforms to help agricultural companies report on their value chains. "Scope 3 reporting" in the CSRD is the requirement for companies to report indirect Greenhouse Gas emissions across their value chain. Scope 2 involves indirect emissions from purchased energy, such as electricity, steam, heat, and cooling. Scope 1 is the reporting of direct greenhouse gas emissions from a company's owned or controlled assets.
- The **Corporate Sustainability Due Diligence Directive (CSDDD - 2024/1720)** entered into force on 25 July 2024, following which Member States have two years to transpose it into national legislation. It will apply to large companies 2 years after that and small companies after 4 years. It will oblige these companies to take action to identify, prevent, mitigate, and remediate adverse human rights and environmental impacts within their operations and value chains ([link](#)). It will apply to a narrower set of larger EU companies (and certain non-EU companies); i.e. those with >1000 employees and > EUR 450 million turnover (net) worldwide. and non-EU companies with > EUR 450 million turnover (net) in the EU. It covers the full "chain of activities". Article 20 indicates that Member States should also support companies and their business partners by setting up, individually or jointly, dedicated websites to help with the reporting requirements and model contract clauses ensuring due diligence. Article 21 promises that the Commission will establish a single EU help desk to assist with similar issues. The CSDDD specifically highlights the **environmental issues** that companies need to consider: a) **climate change**: companies must assess their impact on climate change and take measures to align with the Paris Agreement goals, b) **pollution**: Impacts on water, air, and soil quality must be assessed and mitigated; c) **resource use**: companies need to consider their use of natural resources and promote sustainable resource management, d) **biodiversity**: Impacts on biodiversity and ecosystems need to be identified and addressed.

A third piece of legislation is the **Sustainable Finance Disclosures Regulation (SFDR)** which aims at promoting transparency and preventing greenwashing in the financial market. It requires financial market participants, like investment firms and financial advisors, to disclose how they incorporate sustainability considerations into their investment decisions and products. It helps investors identify companies and projects which are supporting sustainability objectives to make informed choices. The SFDR is also designed to allow investors to properly assess how sustainability risks are integrated in the investment decision process. In this way, the SFDR contributes to one of the EU's big political objectives: attracting private funding to help Europe make the shift to a net-zero economy. Changes in this draft Regulation are proposed in 2025. Part of this initiative is the Commission's [intention to rate](#) the Environmental Social and Governance performance of companies according to a quantitative scale. The SFDR introduces the concept of Principal Adverse Impact indicators as a means of measuring the adverse impacts of companies' investments on the environment and wider society. PAI indicators are presented in Annex I of SFDR level 2 and consist of mandatory Environmental and Social indicators in table 1, and additional opt-in [Environmental PAI](#).

A fourth initiative is the "**Framework to Facilitate Sustainable Investment**" (aka SFI or the Taxonomy Regulation [2020/852](#)), which includes investments in sustainable forest management and also stresses (Article 10) *strengthening land carbon sinks, including through avoiding deforestation and forest degradation, restoration of forests, sustainable management and restoration of croplands, grasslands and wetlands, afforestation, and regenerative agriculture*. The "Climate Delegated Act" for this Regulation ([2121/2131](#)) mentions "forest" 641 times but fails to mention the importance of trees outside forests. Nor does it include sustainable agricultural practices. EURAF [Policy Briefing #28](#) (December 2023) tried to rectify this by proposing a structure for "agroforestry management plans" but no response has been received from the responsible DG (FISMA). The SFI indicates the key areas for sustainability reporting: Article 11 - substantial contribution to climate change adaptation, Article 12 -

substantial contribution to the sustainable use and protection of water and marine resources, Article 13 - substantial contribution to the transition to a circular economy, Article 14 - substantial contribution to pollution prevention and control, Article 15 - substantial contribution to the protection of biodiversity and restoration of ecosystems. The Taxonomy remains under continuous review (although still without inclusion of agroforestry in the Climate Delegated Act!), with a recent 350 pages [report](#) produced by the EU Platform on Sustainable Finance and new consultation [open to 5.2.25](#).

A fifth element in the rather crowded sustainability landscape is the [draft Green Claims Directive](#) (aka “Directive on substantiation and communication of explicit environmental claims”) which helps deliver a commitment in the Green Deal ([COM/2019/640](#)) to tackle false environmental claims by ensuring that buyers receive reliable, comparable and verifiable information to enable them to make more sustainable decisions and to reduce the risk of ‘greenwashing’. A “[general approach](#)” was agreed by Council in June 2024, and it is expected to be in the Commission work programme for 2025. Companies will be obliged to use clear criteria and the latest scientific evidence to substantiate their claims and labels. Environmental claims and labels should be clear and easy to understand, with a specific reference to the environmental characteristics they cover (such as durability, recyclability or biodiversity).

Why is agroforestry important for Corporate Sustainability Reporting?

1. Climate Change Mitigation

EURAF calculates that neutrality in the land sector is possible for the EU by 2040, but only if there is a massive planting programme of Trees outside the Forest¹.

This should focus on areas where trees can bring the biggest environmental and carbon sequestration benefits, and where there is least reduction in agricultural production. EURAF calculates that there are 95.2 million hectares of cropland and pastureland in the EU-27 that are devoid of trees, and 117.9 million hectares with less than 10% tree-crown-cover. Bringing these areas to the 10% tree-crown-cover threshold common for agroforestry systems worldwide would mean planting 11.2 million ha of agroforestry, or an area equivalent to the size of Bulgaria.

Farmers and foresters should be rewarded through the voluntary Carbon Removals Certification Framework, and also through a statutory agricultural/forestry Emission Trading Scheme. Find details in EURAF [Policy Briefing #26](#)

2. Climate Change Adaptation

Agroforestry is mentioned in the adaptation strategies or plans of only 11 EU Member States, despite the extensive scientific literature on its benefits. EURAF commends the Adaptation Plans of Czechia, France, Italy and Slovakia as examples of good practice, and encourages other EU Member States to introduce measures focused on i) improved carbon sequestration; ii) reduced soil erosion, increased fertility and resource use efficiency; iii) greater resistance to droughts and floods; iv) diversified landscapes and biodiversity; v) reduced pest and disease pressure; vi) maintained crop yields and animal welfare; vii) increased resilience to extreme events, including droughts, wildfires and storms; viii) improved economic diversity and benefits; and ix) reduced groundwater and air pollution. Agroforestry can deliver on all these criteria: see [Policy Briefing #27](#) for details and references.

3. Sustainable Water Resources

Mixtures of trees and agriculture in upland catchments increase the water holding capacity of soils and reduce stormwater flows. Riparian strips and lines of trees, established in a network of berms and swales, contribute to floodwater dispersal and management. In drought-prone areas, trees can be established after contour ripping, and combined with the establishment of lagoons to conserve water supply locally.

Well-designed, tree-rich landscapes evaporate rainfall and help it to fall again in downwind catchments. That evapotranspiration helps cool our continent if carried out at a big enough scale.

EURAF recommends the opportunity for hydrologic bioengineering at landscape scale, and we invite much greater cooperation between local authorities, river-authorities and farmer groups in the planning and planting of

¹ Each Member State has its own definition of “forest land” EURAF also argues that there should be an integrated Rural cadastre to link national databases of Forestry and Agricultural land ([Policy Briefing #15](#))

agroforestry and landscape features, in line with the objectives of the upcoming EU Water resilience initiative (see [Policy Briefing #64](#)).

[4. Soil, water and atmospheric pollution](#)

Agroforestry trees have clear benefits to soil health, water quality and atmospheric pollution directly by i) binding soils in place, reducing water erosion, ii) reducing wind speeds and so lessening windborne soil erosion, including dust plumes and atmospheric pollution from phytochemicals, iii) absorbing excess nutrients, and iv) slowing down pollutant migration through soils to groundwater, and indirectly by boosting soil fertility and pest predation pressure, and so lessening the extent of fertiliser and phytosanitation use.

The Directive on Soil Monitoring and Resilience will help standardise soil monitoring methods in the EU Member States, but much greater help is needed to encourage farmers and foresters to record field-by-field information on soil carbon, fertiliser use and soil nutrient content. Data collected should be free for all farmers, and held in open databases linked to i) the long-delayed Farm Sustainability Tool for Nutrients and ii) the CAP Land Parcel Identification System. This detailed information can provide a basis for environmental “payment by result” schemes linked to carbon sequestration, GHG emissions reductions, soil health indicators, groundwater impacts and atmospheric pollutant emissions. See [Policy Briefing #65](#) for more details.

[5. Protection of Biodiversity and Ecosystems](#)

Progress towards targets in the EU 2030 Biodiversity Strategy and the Nature Restoration Regulation is restricted by the current pressure on both agriculture and forestry. EURAF suggests a massive planting of trees in lines and small groups on agricultural land that can allow agricultural yields to be maintained, animal welfare to be improved and trees to be put to productive use in a way which makes landscapes more structurally and biologically diverse.

EURAF’s mission is to work with the public and private sector to ensure that all areas of grassland and cropland in Europe have 10% tree-crown-cover by 2040. This needs a much stronger focus on planting trees on areas of mineral soil beset by problems of erosion and soil degradation. We call for the active participation of national and local governments in setting and monitoring these targets, particularly for local authority regions most bereft of trees on agricultural lands, which are further discussed in [Policy Briefing #66](#).

[6. The Circular Economy](#)

The circular economy in agriculture means food systems that build natural capital and allow nature to thrive. Agroforestry is a regenerative form of agriculture which mixes food and wood products in ways that generate positive outcomes for nature, such as healthy and stable soils, enhanced local biodiversity, and improved air or water quality. It can be tailored to local contexts and merged with other practices such as more diverse crop varieties, keyline planting design, cover crops, adaptive multi-paddock grazing, and living barns.

It creates a mosaic of trees, crops and animals which more closely resemble natural ecosystems, and provides a habitat for a wider range of organisms. It also delivers a greater range of multiple products: for example, regular pruning improves wood quality, boosts crop yields, and generates animal feed and wood chips. Silvopastoral systems reduce the greenhouse gas, ammonia and nitrate emissions associated with livestock. Silvoarable systems maximise use of soil, water and nutrient resources. But sustainable farming practices only make economic sense if their environmental and carbon benefits are accurately accounted. We therefore call on the next CAP to improve its environmental “performance monitoring and modelling metrics”, and implement payments by environmental results, which also recognise the past environmental efforts of farmers, in ways that are further discussed in [Policy Briefing #67](#)

EURAF recently published “**Agricultural trees for resilient landscapes: a vision for European agroforestry**” ([EURAF, December 2024](#)) this gives 17 recommendations to the Commission and Member States for the encouragement of agroforestry in the EU.

This Policy Briefing is an output from the [DigitAF Project](#) Grant agreement: 101059794. DigitAF is a consortium of 26 European and international partners committed to providing digital tools to boost Agroforestry in Europe to meet climate, biodiversity and sustainable farming goals. Views and opinions expressed are those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

